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New Ideas In Cancer's Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy

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1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Stable-Decompositions pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. ((Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the

conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if
it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic
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SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions
SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic
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such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme
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Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegancy and the significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. The "Cancer's Recognition" are the under research to figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These types are all officially called "SuperHyperVertex" but the relations amid them all officially called "SuperHyperEdge". The frameworks "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" are chosen and elected to research about "Cancer's Recognition". Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues to research on theoretical segments and "Cancer's Recognition". Some avenues are posed to pursue this research. It's also officially collected in the form of some questions and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is a maximal Neutrosophic of

SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It's redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, "The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" with the key points, "The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet", "The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices", "The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints". To get structural examples and instances, I'm going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It's the main. It'll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperStable-Decompositions until the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then it's officially called a "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" but otherwise, it isn't a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions are redefined to a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.] SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions or the strongest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, called SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and the strongest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognition" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances' styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a

SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. There isn't any formation of any
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions but literarily, it's the deformation of any
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the "amount of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the "amount of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the "Cancer's Recognition" in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It's motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled "SuperHyperGraphs". Thus it motivates us to define different types of "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" on "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, "Cancer's Recognition", more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection "Preliminaries", initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what's going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, are figured out in sections "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Stable-Decompositions to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what's done in this section, titled "Results on SuperHyperClasses" and "Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses". As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in the sections "Results on SuperHyperClasses" and "Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses". The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section "General Results". Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, "General Results", "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions", "Results on SuperHyperClasses" and "Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses". There are curious questions about what's done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word "best" as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, "SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". The keyword of this research debut in the section "Applications in Cancer's Recognition" with two cases and subsections "Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel" and "Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel". In the section,

“Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [131],Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [131],Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [131],Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [131],Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](Ref. [131], Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [131],Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths](Ref. [131],Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)](Ref. [131],Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [131].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [131],Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Stable-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [131],Definition 2.2,p.2).

Let X be a Stable-Decompositions of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\begin{aligned} T_A(X) &= \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ I_A(X) &= \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}, \\ \text{and } F_A(X) &= \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}. \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i' 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;

- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 402
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 403
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 404
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 406
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- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 408
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If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 410
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Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.7, p.3). 412

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 413
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- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$; 415
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$; 416
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$; 417
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$. 418

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 419

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 420
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- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 422
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 423
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- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 425
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- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 427
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- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 429
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 430

$$(vii) \sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V, (i = 1, 2, \dots, n);$$

$$(viii) \sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V, (i' = 1, 2, \dots, n').$$

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [131], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;

- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 473
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- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; 476
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- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. 479
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Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold: 482
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- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 485
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 486
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 487
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 488
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 489
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 490
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 491
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 492
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 493
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Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 495

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 496

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 497
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 498
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 499
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 500
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Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). (Ref. [131], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$.

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [131], Definition 5.4, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall E'_a, E'_b : E'_a \text{ and } E'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions criteria** holds

$$\forall V'_a, V'_b : V'_a \text{ and } V'_b \text{ are Stable};$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Decompositions).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme

SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

(i) an δ -**SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)| &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)| &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

(ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2)

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions more Neutrosophically understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions** if the Table (3) holds.

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

4 Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Neutrosophic event).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Any Neutrosophic k -subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Neutrosophic subset of A of V is called **Neutrosophic event**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Neutrosophic Independent).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. s Neutrosophic k -events A_i , $i \in I$ is called **Neutrosophic s -independent** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Neutrosophic k -events of A and B is called **Neutrosophic independent criteria**. The following expression is called **Neutrosophic independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Neutrosophic Variable).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Any k -function Stable-Decompositions like E is called **Neutrosophic k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Stable-Decompositions like E is called **Neutrosophic Variable**.

The notion of independent on Neutrosophic Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Neutrosophic Expectation).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Expectation** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Neutrosophic Crossing).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A Neutrosophic number is called **Neutrosophic Crossing** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let m and n propose special Stable-Decompositions. Then with $m \geq 4n$,

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Neutrosophic random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Neutrosophic independently with probability Stable-Decompositions $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Neutrosophic number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Neutrosophic Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

□

Theorem 4.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

Proof. Form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between conseDecompositionive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$. □

Theorem 4.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Neutrosophic number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between conseDecompositionive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel

SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n - 1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n - 1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k - n)^3/64n^2$ by the Neutrosophic Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. $\square$

Proposition 4.9. *Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X be a nonnegative Neutrosophic Variable and t a positive real number. Then*

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. *Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Stable-Decompositions $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.*

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. *Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.*

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k + 1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Neutrosophic Variable for this Neutrosophic Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k + 1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k + 1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1 - p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1 - p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$. 788

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p} (k+1)^{\text{choose } 2}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{n e^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $n e^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . 789
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Definition 4.12. (Neutrosophic Variance). 794

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. A Neutrosophic k -Variable E has a number is called **Neutrosophic Variance** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic Variance criteria** 795
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$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 799
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X be a Neutrosophic Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 802
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let X_n be a Neutrosophic Variable in a probability Stable-Decompositions (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then 805
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$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. 810
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Theorem 4.15. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k) 2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$. 815
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Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. 820
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Corollary 4.16. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either:

(i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* .

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 4.17. (Neutrosophic Threshold).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let P be a monotone property of SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a **Neutrosophic Threshold** for P is a function $f(n)$ such that:

(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P ,

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P .

Definition 4.18. (Neutrosophic Balanced).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let F be a fixed Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a copy of F as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Neutrosophic Balanced**.

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. Let F be a nonempty balanced Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F as a Neutrosophic SubSuperHyperGraph.

Proof. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 4.20. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}_{i=1}^4\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,4}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,4}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}_{i=1}^4\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,4}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,4}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

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Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}_{i=1}^4\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,3}, \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2,3}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_4, E_3, E_2\}, \{E_5, E_3, E_2\}, \{E_1, E_3\}, \{E_i\}\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i, V_j\}_{V_i \in \{V_1, V_2, N, F\}, V_j \in \{V_4, O, H\}}, \\
 & \{V_3, O\}, \{V_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

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Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 5. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{E_i\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_a, V_b, V_c, V_d\}_{a \in \{1,2,3,4\}, b \in \{6,7,8\}, c \in \{9,10,11,12\}, d \in \{13,14,15\}, \{V_i\}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^2.$$

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- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}$$

$$\{E_{2i+2_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}, \{E_{ab+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{E_i\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}}$$

$$= \{\{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}$$

$$\{V_{2i+2_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}, \{V_{ab+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{V_i\}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= z^4.$$

Figure 6. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &\{ \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}, \\
 &\{E_{ab+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{E_i\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &\{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}, \\
 &\{V_{ab+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{V_i\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

Figure 7. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{E_1, E_2, E_3\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}}, \{E_a\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{V_a, V_b, V_c\}_{a \in \{1,2,3\}, b \in \{4,5,6,7\}, c \in \{8,9,10,11\}}, \\
 &= \{V_d, V_e\}_{V_d \in E_i, V_e \in E_j, i \neq j, i, j \neq 4}, \{V_f\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+2_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}, \{E_{a+b+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{E_i\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^4. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 &= \{\{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\} \\
 &= \{V_{2i+2_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}, \{V_{a+b+c_a, b \geq 3}\}, \{V_i\}\}. \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 8. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{\{E_1, E_2, E_3\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j \in \{1,2,3\}}, \{E_a\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 & z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{\{V_a, V_b, V_c\}_{a \in \{1,2,3\}, b \in \{4,5,6,7\}, c \in \{8,9,10,11\}}, \\
 & \{V_d, V_e\}_{V_d \in E_i, V_e \in E_j, i \neq j, i, j \neq 4}, \{V_f\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 & z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

Figure 9. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 10. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 11. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophicly straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{ \{E_6, E_7, E_8\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j \in \{6,7,8\}}, \{E_k\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 & = z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{ \{V_1, V_{6(4)}\}, \{V_2, V_{6(5)}\}, \{V_3, V_{5(4)}\}, \{V_k\} \}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 & = z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

Figure 12. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}_{i=2,3,4,5,6}\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{E_i\}_{i=2,3,4,5,6}, \{E_i\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{V_a\}_{a=4,5,6,9,10}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{V_a\}_{a=2,3,4,5,6}, \{V_b\}_{b=1,2,3,7,8}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{V_a\}_{b=1,2,3,7,8}, \{V_c\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} = \\
 &= z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

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Figure 13. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{\{E_6, E_7, E_8\}, \{E_i, E_j\}_{i,j\{6,7,8\}}, \{E_k\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
 & \{\{V_1, V_{6(4)}\}, \{V_2, V_{6(5)}\}, \{V_3, V_{5(4)}\}, \{V_k\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 &= z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} & \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 &= z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} & \\
 &= \{\{V_2, V_3\}, \{V_a\}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 &= z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 14. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, \{E_j\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_{2i+2_{i=0^1}}, V_5\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{V_{2i+2_{i=0^1}}, V_5\}, \{V_a\}\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, \{E_j\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_1, V_3, V_{10}, V_{22}\}, \dots\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= az^b.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 16. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, \{E_j\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^b. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^2}}, \{E_j\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{\{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}, \dots\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^b. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 17. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 18. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 19. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{ \{E_{2i+1, i=0^5}\}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1, i=0^5}\}, \{E_i\} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{ \{V_{E_{2i+1, i=0^5}}\}, B \subseteq \{V_{E_{2i+1, i=0^5}}\}, \{V_a\} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^3. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{ \{E_i\} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\ &= \{ \{ \text{INTERNAL SuperHyperVERTICES} \} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= az^b. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 20. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is

Figure 21. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Figure 22. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.3)

Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{E_{2i+2_{i=0^1}}\}, A \subseteq \{E_{2i+2_{i=0^1}}\}, \{E_i\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{V_a, V_b, V_c, V_d \\
 & \quad \} V_a \in \{R, P, M, J, V_1\}, V_b \in \{H_6, O_6, E_6, C_6\}, V_c \in \{S_6, R_6, T_6, V_7, V_8, V_9\}, V_d \in \{T_3, S_3, U_3, V_4, V_5\} \}, \\
 & \quad \{V_a\} \}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

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Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct

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Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHypeNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

Proposition 4.23. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions is at least*

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions.

Proposition 4.24. *Assume a simple Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Neutrosophic number of type-result-R-Stable-Decompositions has, the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality, is the Neutrosophic cardinality of*

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's a Neutrosophic type-result-R-Stable-Decompositions with the least Neutrosophic cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for cardinality.

Proposition 4.25. *Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Is a Neutrosophic type-result-Stable-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic type-result-Stable-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions since neither amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of

SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality indicates that these Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Neutrosophic lower bound in the term of Neutrosophic sharpness. In other words, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}} \cdot$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Neutrosophic structure of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions decorates the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Neutrosophic connections

so as this Neutrosophic style implies different versions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Neutrosophic bound is to have the maximum Neutrosophic groups of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have perfect Neutrosophic connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph arising from its Neutrosophic properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, then there's no Neutrosophic connection. Furthermore, the Neutrosophic existence of one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no Neutrosophic effect to talk about the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. Since at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Neutrosophic background of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge but at least two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices make the Neutrosophic version of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Neutrosophic setting of non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Neutrosophic adjective for the initial Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Neutrosophic appearance of the loop Neutrosophic version of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and this Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Neutrosophic adjective "loop" on the basic Neutrosophic framework engages one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Neutrosophic setting. With these Neutrosophic bases, on a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions has the Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions has the Neutrosophic cardinality at least a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions since either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Neutrosophic usage of this Neutrosophic framework and even more there's no Neutrosophic connection inside or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's a Neutrosophic contradiction with the term "Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions" since the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality never happens for this Neutrosophic style of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Neutrosophic connection inside as mentioned in first Neutrosophic case in the forms of drawback for this selected Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Comes up. This Neutrosophic case implies having the Neutrosophic style of on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style on the every Neutrosophic elements of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that some Neutrosophic amount of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style. The Neutrosophic cardinality of the v SuperHypeSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}$$

But the lower Neutrosophic bound is up. Thus the minimum Neutrosophic cardinality of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality ends up the Neutrosophic discussion. The first Neutrosophic term refers to the Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperClass of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Neutrosophic style amid some amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. This Neutrosophic setting of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel proposes a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet has only some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Neutrosophic amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The Neutrosophic cardinality of this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Neutrosophic case is occurred in the minimum Neutrosophic situation. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Contains some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices taken from the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

It means that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as used Neutrosophic background in the Neutrosophic terms of worst Neutrosophic case and the common theme of the lower Neutrosophic bound occurred in the specific Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are Neutrosophic free-quasi-triangle.

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Then every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has at least no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. Those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in a Neutrosophic style-R-Stable-Decompositions. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions but with slightly differences in the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality amid those Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Neutrosophic cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. Let $Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

But with the slightly differences,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions} = \\ \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \stackrel{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}, \end{aligned}$$

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ for all Neutrosophic intended SuperHyperVertices but in a Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, then the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions is at least the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions in some cases but the maximum number of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Neutrosophic number of Neutrosophic

SuperHyperVertices, has the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. 1010
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The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Neutrosophic optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but this Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions where the Neutrosophic completion of the Neutrosophic incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, a Neutrosophic embedded R-Stable-Decompositions. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality and they're Neutrosophic SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Neutrosophic style of the embedded Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. The interior types of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Neutrosophic number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices pose the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. Thus Neutrosophic exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and in Neutrosophic SuperHyperRelation with the interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions, there's the usage of exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. The Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions with the inclusion of all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, is a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices in an Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions, minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. 1012
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The main definition of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions has two titles. a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions and its corresponded quasi-maximum Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For 1060
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any Neutrosophic number, there's a Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions with that quasi-maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, then the Neutrosophic quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositionss for all Neutrosophic numbers less than its Neutrosophic corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositionss acted on the all possible used formations of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Neutrosophic number. This Neutrosophic number is

considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Stable-Decompositionss. Let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet and a Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions is re-formalized and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal technical definition for the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions poses the upcoming expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised. 1084

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

And then, 1085

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook. 1086

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}, \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{ S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}, \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\
|S_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, "Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood", could be redefined as the collection of the 1090 1091

Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. It's, literarily, another name for "Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Decompositions" but, precisely, it's the generalization of "Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Decompositions" since "Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Decompositions" happens "Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions" in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but "Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood" may not happens "Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions" in a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, "Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood", "Neutrosophic Quasi-Stable-Decompositions", and "Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions" are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}$, $N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}}$ be a Neutrosophic number, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &\quad |N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \}. \end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} \{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}}} z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}} [z_{\text{Neutrosophic Number}}]_{\text{Neutrosophic Class}} \mid \\ &|N_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

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To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

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The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is an **Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge amid some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions** is related to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There's not only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn't have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet since they've come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Stable-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some amount Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions. There isn't only less than two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the

Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Neutrosophic free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Neutrosophic on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Neutrosophic stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions amid those obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices belong to any Neutrosophic quasi-R-Stable-Decompositions if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, some interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices are mutually Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors with no Neutrosophic exception at all minus all Neutrosophic SuperHypeNeighbors to any amount of them.

Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Neutrosophic numbers of those Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from that Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge excluding more than r distinct Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Neutrosophic bound for Neutrosophic cardinality. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. Since it doesn't have

the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions. Since it **doesn't do** the Neutrosophic procedure such that such that there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, titled its Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Neutrosophic procedure"]. There's only **one** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Neutrosophic pairs are titled Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the

maximum Neutrosophic SuperHyperCardinality of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge to have some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Neutrosophic R-Stable-Decompositions only contains all interior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices from the unique Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Stable-Decompositions, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions. The

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1186

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

is the simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1187
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an **Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. But the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1190
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions **is** up. To sum them up, the Neutrosophic 1202
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SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions. Since the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for some Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices given by that Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions **and** it's an Neutrosophic **Stable-Decompositions**. Since it's **the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality** of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge for all Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions, 1221

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet of the Neutrosophic 1222
Stable-Decompositions, not: 1223

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, not: 1224

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Neutrosophic 1225
SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious 1226
simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSet called the 1227

“Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions” 1228

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Neutrosophic type-SuperHyperSets called the 1229

Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions, 1230

is only and only 1231

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-Decompositions} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicQuasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-Decompositions} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{NeutrosophicR-Quasi-Stable-DecompositionsSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

In a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □ 1232

5 The Neutrosophic Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 5.1. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{E_{2i+1}{}_{2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}\}, \\
 &A \subseteq \{E_{2i+1}{}_{2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}, \{E_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{V_{2i+1}{}_{2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}^{INTERNAL}\}, \\
 &A \subseteq \{V_{2i+1}{}_{2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}^{INTERNAL}, \{V_a\}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Example (16.5)

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$.
Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ E_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|} \} \}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{ E_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}, \{ E_i \} \}. \\
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ V_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}^{INTERNAL} \} \}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{ V_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}|}^{INTERNAL}, \{ V_a \} \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|ESHG|}, V_{|ESHG|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{E_i\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
&= \{\{V_i^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}, A \subseteq \{V_i^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}, \{V^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= z^3.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
\text{CENTER}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
E_2, \text{CENTER}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. &
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.
The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
\cdots, \\
E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 5.8. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

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Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

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Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Example (16.11)

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges\}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges\}, \\
 & \{E_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{\{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices\}, \\
 & B \subseteq \{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices\}, \\
 & \{V_i\}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

Figure 27. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Example (16.13)

$ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ E_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}^*|}^* \}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{ E_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}^*|}^*, \{ E_i^* \} \}. \\
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3. \\
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions}} \\
 &= \{ \{ V_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}^*|}^{INTERNAL} \}, \\
 & A \subseteq \{ V_{2i+1, 2i+1=|E_{NSHG}^*|}^{INTERNAL}, \{ V_a \} \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-Stable-Decompositions SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 & CENTER, E_2^*
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2^*, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in the Neutrosophic Example (16.15)

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperStable-Decompositions proposes some longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.12. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, some general results are introduced.

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets.

Corollary 6.2. Assume Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable – Decompositions} = \\ & \{ \text{the SuperHyperStable – Decomposition of the SuperHyperVertices} \mid \\ & \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ & \text{SuperHyperStable – Decompositions} \\ & | \text{Neutrosophic cardinality among those SuperHyperStable – Decompositions.} \} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively. 1360
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Corollary 6.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and SuperHyperStable-Decompositions coincide. 1363
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Corollary 6.4. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseDecompositionive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if and only if it's a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1366
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Corollary 6.5. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseDecompositionive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions if and only if it's a longest SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1370
1371
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Corollary 6.6. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and reversely. 1374
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Corollary 6.7. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and reversely. 1377
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Corollary 6.8. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions isn't well-defined. 1382
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Corollary 6.9. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions isn't well-defined. 1385
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Corollary 6.10. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions isn't well-defined. 1388
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Corollary 6.11. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is well-defined. 1393
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Corollary 6.12. Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is well-defined. 1396
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Corollary 6.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Decompositions is well-defined. 1399
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Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then V is 1404
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- (i) : the dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1406
- (ii) : the strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1407
- (iii) : the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1408
- (iv) : the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1409
- (v) : the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1410
- (vi) : the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1411

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is 1412

- (i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1414
- (ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1415
- (iii) : the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1416
- (iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1417
- (v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1418
- (vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1419

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is 1420

- (i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1422
- (ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1423
- (iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1424
- (iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1425
- (v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1426
- (vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1427

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1428

- (i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1431
- (ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1432
- (iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1433
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1434
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1435
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1436

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1437

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1438

- (i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1440
- (ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1441
- (iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1442
- (iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1443
- (v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1444
- (vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1445
1446

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1447

Proposition 6.19. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of 1448
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- (i) : the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1451
- (ii) : the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1452
- (iii) : the connected SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1453
- (iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1454
- (v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1455
- (vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1456

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1457
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Proposition 6.20. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of 1459
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- (i) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1461
- (ii) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1462
- (iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1463
- (iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1464
- (v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1465
- (vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1466

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1467
1468

Proposition 6.21. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a 1469
1470
1471
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- (i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1474
- (ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1475

- (iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1476
- (iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1477
- (v) : *strong* $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1478
- (vi) : *connected* $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1479
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Proposition 6.22. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a* 1481
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- (i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1487
- (ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1488
- (iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1489
- (iv) : δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1490
- (v) : *strong* δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1491
- (vi) : *connected* δ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1492

Proposition 6.23. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of* 1493
1494
1495
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- (i) : *dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1497
- (ii) : *strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1498
- (iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1499
- (iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1500
- (v) : *strong* $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1501
- (vi) : *connected* $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -*dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1502
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is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1504
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Proposition 6.24. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual* 1508
1509

- (i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1510
- (ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1511
- (iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1512

(iv) : *SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1513

(v) : *strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1514

(vi) : *connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1515

Proposition 6.25. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Neutrosophic number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$.* 1516
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Proposition 6.26. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min \Sigma_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual* 1518
1519
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1521

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1522

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1523

(iv) : *($\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1524

(v) : *strong ($\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1525
1526

(vi) : *connected ($\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1527
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Proposition 6.27. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Neutrosophic number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual* 1529
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1532

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1533

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1534

(iv) : *0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1535

(v) : *strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1536

(vi) : *connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1537

Proposition 6.28. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet.* 1538
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Proposition 6.29. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Decompositions/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual* 1540
1541
1542
1543

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1544

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1545

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1546

(iv) : *$\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1547

(v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1548
1549

(vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1550
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Proposition 6.30. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Neutrosophic number is $\min_{\Sigma_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \text{ } t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual* 1552
1553
1554
1555

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1556

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1557

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1558

(iv) : *$(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1559

(v) : *strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions;* 1560
1561

(vi) : *connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.* 1562
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Proposition 6.31. *Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the $ESHGs : (V, E)$ Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs.* 1564
1565
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Proposition 6.32. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that* 1569
1570
1571

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$; 1572

(ii) $vx \in E$. 1573

Proposition 6.33. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then* 1574
1575

(i) S is SuperHyperStable-Decompositions set; 1576

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number. 1577

Proposition 6.34. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then* 1578
1579

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$; 1580

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$. 1581

Proposition 6.35. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then* 1582
1583

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$; 1584

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$. 1585

Proposition 6.36. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then* 1586

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1587
1588
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1589
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1590
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1591
1592

Proposition 6.37. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then 1593

- (i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1594
1595
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1596
1597
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1598
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1599
1600

Proposition 6.38. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then 1601
1602

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1603
1604
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1605
1606
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\}$; 1607
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1608
1609

Proposition 6.39. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then 1610
1611

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1612
1613
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1614
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1615
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1616
1617

Proposition 6.40. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperStar. Then 1618

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1619
- (ii) $\Gamma = 1$; 1620
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c)$; 1621
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1622
1623

Proposition 6.41. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperWheel. Then 1624

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \cdots, v_{i+6}, \cdots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1625
1626
- (ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \cdots, v_{i+6}, \cdots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|$; 1627
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \Sigma_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \cdots, v_{i+6}, \cdots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)$; 1628
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \cdots, v_{i+6}, \cdots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1629
1630

Proposition 6.42. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then 1631

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1632
1633
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$; 1634
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$; 1635
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1636
1637

Proposition 6.43. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then 1638

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1639
1640
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$; 1641
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1642
- (iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1643
1644

Proposition 6.44. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStars with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1645
1646

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \cdots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1647
1648
- (ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1649
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \Sigma_{i=1}^m \Sigma_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1650
- (iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \cdots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1651
1652

Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1653
1654
1655

- (i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1656
1657
- (ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1658
- (iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\Sigma_{s \in S} \Sigma_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1659

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1660
1661

Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1662
1663
1664

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1665
1666

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1667

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1668

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Decompositions for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1669
1670

Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1671
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(i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1673
1674
1675

(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1676
1677
1678

Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1679
1680

(i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1681
1682
1683

(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1684
1685
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Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a $[an]$ $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1687
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1689

(i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1690
1691

(ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1692
1693

(iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1694
1695

(iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1696
1697

Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V]$ -SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1698
1699
1700

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1701
1702
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1703
1704
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1705
1706
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1707
1708

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1709
1710
1711

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1712
1713
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1714
1715
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1716
1717
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1718
1719

Proposition 6.52. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1720
1721
1722

- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1723
1724
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1725
1726
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1727
1728
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1729
1730

Proposition 6.53. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then following statements hold; 1731
1732
1733

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1734
1735
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1736
1737
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1738
1739
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1740
1741

Proposition 6.54. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] 1742
 $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph which is 1743
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. Then following statements hold; 1744*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive 1745
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1746*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1747
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1748*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive 1749
SuperHyperStable-Decompositions; 1750*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 1751
2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. 1752*

7 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's 1753 Neutrosophic Recognition 1754

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure 1755
out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of 1756
this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some 1757
parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the 1758
cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the 1759
cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease. 1760

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease. 1761

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in 1762
the long-term Neutrosophic function. 1763

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the 1764
Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long 1765
Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. 1766
Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some 1767
determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the 1768
cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be 1769
Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's 1770
happened and what's done. 1771

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which 1772
are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. 1773
The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and 1774
between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic 1775
SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, SuperHyperStar, 1776
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to 1777
find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions or the 1778
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions in those Neutrosophic 1779
Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. 1780

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

8 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (29), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions.

Question 10.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer's recognitions? 1811
1812

Question 10.2. Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions? 1813
1814
1815

Question 10.3. Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them? 1816
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Question 10.4. Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions? 1818
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Problem 10.5. The SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer's recognitions and they're based on SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, are there else? 1821
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Problem 10.6. Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results? 1824
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Problem 10.7. What's the independent research based on Cancer's recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions? 1826
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11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks 1828

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted. 1829
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This research uses some approaches to make Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it's mentioned on the title "Cancer's Recognitions". To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperStable-Decompositions, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperStable-Decompositions and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognitions" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called " SuperHyperStable-Decompositions" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6), benefits and avenues for this research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out. 1832
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Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperStable-Decompositions	
3. Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Decompositions	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer's Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

12 Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

(i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;

(ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

(iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;

(iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{NSHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

(v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

(i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;

(ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic

- v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality;
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality

consequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperDuality, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperDuality, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

straightforward.

1977

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1978

1979

1980

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1981

1982

1983

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1984

1985

1986

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{3i+24^3_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1^7_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1987

1988

1989

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

1990

1991

straightforward.

1992

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1993

1994

1995

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1996

1997

1998

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

1999

2000

2001

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2002

2003

2004

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

2005

2006

straightforward.

2007

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_5, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2008

2009

2010

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2011

2012

2013

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2014

2015

2016

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2017

2018

2019

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (1 \times 1 \times 2)z.$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically

2020

2021

straightforward.

2022

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (2 \times 2 \times 2)z.$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2023

2024

2025

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{2i+1_{i=0}^5}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^6.$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2026

2027

2028

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2029

2030

2031

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z.$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

2032

2033

2034

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses.

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Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
&= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}, \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
& \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
&= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

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Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any

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solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 2088

Example 12.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality. 2089
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Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then 2095
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 & = \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 & = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) choose |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
 & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 & = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| choose 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2097

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2098
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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 2100
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straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied.
 There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one
 SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
 minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any
 solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.
 The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic
 result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27),
 is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}^*, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z^* &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z^*. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDuality.

13 Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin;

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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

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SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; 2208
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(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2211
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(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperJoin, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperJoin, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. 2221
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Example 13.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 2232
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- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2234
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus 2244
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the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin. 2251
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2253
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2256
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2258

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2259
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2262
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2265
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2268
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2271
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2274
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2276

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2277
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2280
2281
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2283
2284
2285

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2286
2287
2288

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2289
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2292
2293
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2295
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2298
2299
2300

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2301
2302
2303

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2304
2305
2306

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2307
2308
2309

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2310
2311
2312

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2313
2314

Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
 straightforward. □

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL}^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperJoin.

14 Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

(i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;

(ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

(iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;

(iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

(v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic

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SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that
they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect; 2486
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(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the
Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2489
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(viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperPerfect, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperPerfect,
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperPerfect and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients
defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of
the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high
Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges
and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic
SuperHyperPerfect; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its
Neutrosophic coefficient. 2499
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Example 14.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair
 $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 2510
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- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly
straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but
 E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic
SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor,
there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic
SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the
Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic
SuperHyperPerfect. 2512
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic
SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly
straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges
but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic
SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that
there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus
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the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect. 2529
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2531
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2534
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2537
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2540
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2543
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2546
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2549
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2552
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2555
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 3 \times 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2558
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2561
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2564
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2567
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2570
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2573
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2576
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2579
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=03}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=05}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2582
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2585
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2588
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2591
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Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
 & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
 & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 & = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 & = \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
 There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
 straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet,
 by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in
 the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 14.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \\
 & \{\}, \\
 & \text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \\
 &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
 & \quad z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in PESHG:(V,E)|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in PESHG:(V,E)|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
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- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperTotal, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperTotal, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
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Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2812
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2815
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2818
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2821
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly straightforward. 2824
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophicly 2827
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2845
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2848
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2851
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2854
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2857
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2860
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2863
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 2866
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 2869
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Proposition 15.4. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then* 2871
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2873

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\ \dots \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &\quad \cdot^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} \cdot^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} V_i^{EXTERNAL} |_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}-1} \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle
 $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{EXTERNAL} ESHG:(V,E)}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\
 &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\
 & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal}} \\
 &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} - 1) z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperTotal.

16 Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected** if 2977
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such 2978
that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ 2979
- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected** if 2980
 $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E',$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j;$ $\forall E_i, E_j \in E',$ such 2981
that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j;$ and 2982
 $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2983
- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected** if 2984
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such 2985
that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ 2986
- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected** if 2987
 $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V',$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a;$ $\forall V_i, V_j \in V',$ such that 2988
 $V_i, V_j \notin E_a;$ and 2989
 $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$ 2990
- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2991
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2992
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected. 2993

Definition 16.2. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperConnected). 2994

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 2995
a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 2996

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 2997
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 2998
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and 2999
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum 3000
Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 3001
of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme 3002
sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such 3003
that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; 3004
- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic 3005
e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic 3006
v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and 3007
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum 3008
Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic 3009
SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive 3010
Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that 3011
they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; 3012
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either 3013
of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, 3014
Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic 3015
rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph 3016
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme 3017
coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality 3018
of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high 3019
Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and 3020
Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme 3021
SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme 3022
coefficient; 3023

- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseDecompositionisive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vi) a **Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseDecompositionisive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperConnected, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperConnected, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseDecompositionisive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

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Example 16.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint. Thus the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3100
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3103
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3106
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3109
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3112
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^{19}, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically 3115
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3133
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3136
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3139
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3142
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=0,11}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3145
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3148
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. 3151
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Neutrosophic approach apply on the upcoming Neutrosophic results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. 3154
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Proposition 16.4. *Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then* 3156
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 3158

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}^{EXTERNAL}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 3159
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$$\begin{aligned}V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ & = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}^z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| = \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}} \in P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, V_b^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_j^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}|} (|P_i^{\text{ESHG:(V,E)}}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Neutrosophic Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Neutrosophic-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (27), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i| E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Neutrosophic\ Cardinality} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Neutrosophic\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Neutrosophic Figure (28), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (28), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them date back on March 09, 2023.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and

SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 3280
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The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [87]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. 3282
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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [132]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic

Graphs” and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [133]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1,2]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions In SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions In SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–55,57–131]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [132,133].

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